

SotA - Service Mesh 24/25

Working Paper, v0.7.6

Author: Detlef Burkhardt <https://orcid.org/0009-0000-9155-716X>
License: CC-BY 4.0
DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.15043102 (Document v0.7.6)
10.5281/zenodo.15043038 (Concept)
Date: March, 2025

DOI Concept Shortlink: y.lab.nrw/sm24

Abstract

This is a State-of-the-Art exploration about Service Mesh Solutions between Q2/2024 and Q1/2025. It analysed ~~10~~ 9 products with around 12 properties in 5 categories:

- Basic Properties
- Interoperability
- Advanced Capabilities
- Strength & Weakness
- Commercial Offerings

9 instead of 10, because the NGINX Service Mesh was archived.

Table of Content

- [SotA - Service Mesh 24/25](#)
 - [Abstract](#)
 - [Table of Content](#)
 - [Introduction](#)
 - [Properties \(overview\)](#)
 - [Basic properties:](#)
 - [Interoperability:](#)
 - [Advanced capabilities:](#)
 - [Strengths & weaknesses](#)
 - [Commercial offers](#)
 - [Product overview](#)
 - [Basic overview](#)
 - [Summaries](#)
 - [Strengths and weaknesses](#)
 - [Basic features comparison](#)
 - [Interoperability comparison](#)
 - [Comparison of advanced properties](#)
 - [Github Numbers \(April/24\)](#)
 - [Products in detail](#)
 - [1. Istio](#)
 - [2. Linkerd](#)
 - [3. Consul Connect](#)
 - [4. AWS App Mesh](#)
 - [5. Service Fabric Mesh](#)
 - [6. Traefik Mesh](#)
 - [7. NGINX Service Mesh](#)
 - [8. Rancher](#)
 - [9. Kuma](#)
 - [10. Cilium](#)
 - [Properties in detail](#)
 - [1. Basic properties:](#)
 - [2. Interoperability](#)
 - [3. Advanced capabilities](#)
 - [4. Strengths and weaknesses](#)
 - [5. Commercial offers](#)
 - [Glossary](#)

Introduction

One of the key advantages of a service mesh is the consistent separation of the technical aspects from the actual business logic. This allows synergies to be leveraged in the technical part and the feature teams to better focus on the business tasks.

While developers concentrate on the actual business logic, the service mesh can transparently handle the necessary technical aspects such as service discovery, load balancing, communication encryption, error handling and performance monitoring. This promotes a clear separation of responsibilities and reduces complexity in the application services themselves.

The business logic does not need to know anything about the details of the data* and control plane*. One of the main advantages of a service mesh is that the so-called sidecar proxies* usually take over all network communication, security and monitoring without the applications themselves having to intervene.

Service meshes are the logical successors to the enterprise service bus. Due to their loose coupling, they fit perfectly into the mindset of a microservice SOA* landscape.

* = See [Glossary](#)

Properties (overview)

The following features characterize a service mesh. For more information, see “General description of properties”.

Basic properties:

1. Routing
2. Security
3. Discovery
4. Observability

Interoperability:

5. Platforms
6. ECS support
7. SMI compliance
8. Multi-mesh
9. Protocols

Advanced capabilities:

10. Rollback
11. Scaling
12. Blue/Green

Strengths & weaknesses

Commercial offers

Product overview

Here is an overview of the 10 service mesh products selected here:

Basic overview

No.	Solution	Manufacturer/Project	License	Homepage	Git-Repo
1	Istio	CNCF	Apache 2.0	https://istio.io/	https://github.com
2	Linkerd	CNCF	Apache 2.0	https://linkerd.io/	https://github.com
3	Consul Connect	HashiCorp / IBM	MPL 2.0	https://www.consul.io/docs/connect	https://github.com
4	AWS App Mesh	AWS	Proprietary	https://aws.amazon.com/app-mesh/	Not public
5	Azure Service Fabric Mesh	Microsoft	Proprietary	https://docs.microsoft.com/en-us/azure/service-fabric-mesh/	Not public
6	Traefik Mesh	Traefik Labs	MPL 2.0	https://traefik.io/mesh/	https://github.com
7	NGINX Service Mesh	F5 Networks	Apache 2.0	https://www.nginx.com/products/nginx-service-mesh/	https://github.com service-mesh
8	Rancher	Rancher Labs / Suse	Apache 2.0	https://rancher.com/	https://github.com
9	Kuma	Kong	Apache 2.0	https://kuma.io/	https://github.com
10	Cilium	Cilium Project	Apache 2.0	https://cilium.io/	https://github.com

Summaries

Strengths and weaknesses

A rough summary of the strengths and weaknesses of each product. Further details can be found in the respective product chapters.

No.	Product	Strengths	Weaknesses
1	Istio	Comprehensive traffic control, integrated telemetry, advanced security features	High complexity, significant resource consumption
2	Linkerd	Easy installation, low resource consumption, transparent proxy implementation	Limited protocol support, restricted extensibility
3	Consul Connect	Seamless integration into the Consul ecosystem, access control intentions	More limited community and resources, security policy complexity
4	AWS App Mesh	Deep AWS integration, simplified microservices management	Limited to AWS environments, feature limitations in multiclusters
5	Azure Service Fabric Mesh	Integrated with Azure services, supports both Windows and Linux containers.	Proprietary, mainly suitable for Azure users.
6	Traefik Mesh	Easy installation, lightweight architecture without sidecars.	Still relatively new with limited feature maturity.
7	NGINX Service Mesh	Advanced load balancing capabilities, integration with existing NGINX infrastructure	No further development, limited future-proofing
8	Rancher	Easy multi-cluster management, cross-platform support	Dependent on Istio, requires extensive knowledge for effective multi-cluster management
9	Kuma	Support for multi-mesh configurations, easy scalability, broad platform support	Configuration complexity in heterogeneous environments, needs stronger community support
10	Cilium	Use of eBPF for high performance, advanced security and networking features	Requires specific technical knowledge, kernel dependencies

Basic features comparison

This table provides a high-level view of the basic features of the different service mesh products. See the individual product sections for more information.

No.	Product	Routing	Security	Discovery	Observability
1	Istio	Sophisticated	Strong	Automatic	Detailed
2	Linkerd	Simple	Automatic mTLS	Automatic	Comprehensive
3	Consul Connect	Simple	TLS-based	Integrated	Metrics, Logs
4	AWS App Mesh	Dynamic	mTLS	AWS Cloud Map	AWS-integrated
5	Azure Service Fabric Mesh	Traffic steering	Azure AD	Azure-specific	Azure-integrated
6	Traefik Mesh	Advanced	mTLS	Built-in	Prom. & Grafana
7	NGINX Service Mesh	Advanced	mTLS	Kubernetes-based	Prometheus & Grafana
8	Rancher	Sophisticated	Strong	Automatic	Granular
9	Kuma	Advanced	mTLS	Integrated	Native integration
10	Cilium	Network-level	Identity-based	Kubernetes-native	Comprehensive

Interoperability comparison

This table provides a comprehensive view of the interoperability characteristics of each service mesh product. See product sections.

No.	Product	Platforms	ECS	SMI	Multi-Mesh	Host/Sidecar	Protocols
1	Istio	Strong	No	Medium	Yes	Envoy	HTTP, HTTP/2, gRPC, TCP, WebSockets, MongoDB
2	Linkerd	Medium	No	Medium	No	Linkerd2-proxy	HTTP, HTTP/2, gRPC
3	Consul Connect	Strong	Yes	Weak	Yes	Both	HTTP, TCP, gRPC
4	AWS App Mesh	Weak	Yes	n/a	No	Envoy	HTTP, HTTP/2, gRPC, TCP
5	Azure Service Fabric Mesh	Weak	No	n/a	No	Envoy	HTTP, TCP
6	Traefik Mesh	Medium	No	Weak	No	Host	HTTP, HTTP/2
7	NGINX Service Mesh	Medium	No	Weak	No	Envoy	HTTP, HTTP/2, gRPC, WebSockets
8	Rancher	Medium	No	Medium	Yes	Envoy	HTTP, HTTP/2, gRPC, TCP, WebSockets
9	Kuma	High	Yes	High	Yes	Envoy	HTTP, HTTP/2, TCP, gRPC
10	Cilium	Medium	No	n/a	No	Host	HTTP, TCP, gRPC, Kafka, DNS

Comparison of advanced properties

An analysis of the values of the advanced features rollback, scaling and blue/green deployment. Details for the respective products.

No.	Product	Rollback	Scaling	Blue/Green
1	Istio	Advanced	Preemptive	Integrated
2	Linkerd	Basic	Dynamic	Supported
3	Consul Connect	Basic	Dynamic	Supported
4	AWS App Mesh	Basic	Dynamic	Supported
5	Azure Service Fabric Mesh	n/a	Manual	n/a
6	Traefik Mesh	n/a	Dynamic	Supported
7	NGINX Service Mesh	Basic	Dynamic	Supported
8	Rancher	Advanced	Preemptive	Integrated
9	Kuma	Advanced	Preemptive	Integrated
10	Cilium	n/a	preemptive	n/a

Github Numbers (April/24)

The following overview shows numbers from github that indicate community activity up to April 27, 2024:

No.	Service Mesh	Stars	Forks	Commits	Created
1	Istio	35,000	7,600	22,791	2016
2	Linkerd	10,400	1,300	6,738	2018
3	Consul Connect	27,800	4,400	21,291	2013
4	AWS App Mesh	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a
5	Azure Service Fabric Mesh	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a
6	Traefik Mesh	2,000	140	419	2020
7	NGINX Service Mesh	94	30	236	n/a
8	Rancher	22,500	2,900	11,815	2014
9	Kuma	3,500	327	6,236	2019
10	Cilium	18,600	2,700	28,541	2017

Products in detail

1. Istio

Istio is a robust, flexible service mesh solution that offers a wide range of network management features in a containerized environment.

Basic features:

1. Routing:

Istio offers sophisticated traffic management, including dynamic load balancing, traffic splitting for A/B testing, and delayed routes for rolling out changes incrementally.

2. Security:

Security is a core feature of Istio. It supports mTLS to encrypt service-to-service communication and provides extensive access controls and security policies.

3. Discovery:

Istio uses the Envoy Proxy to automatically discover services and dynamically adjust network configurations.

4. Observability:

Provides detailed insights into metrics, traces and logs, enabling close monitoring of traffic and system health.

Interoperability:

5. **Platforms:**

Istio is cross-platform and can be deployed on Kubernetes, OpenShift and other platforms that support Docker containers.

6. **ECS support:**

Currently, there is no native support for Amazon's Elastic Container Service (ECS) for Istio; Kubernetes is the main supported platform.

7. **SMI compliance:**

Istio is not directly compliant with the Service Mesh Interface (SMI) specification, which provides a standardized interface for service meshes on Kubernetes.

8. **Multi-mesh:**

Istio supports multi-mesh configurations, which allows multiple independent meshes to be managed and connected.

9. **Protocols**

- Supports HTTP, HTTP/2, gRPC, WebSockets, MongoDB and TCP protocols.
- Can perform protocol detection for specified traffic.

Advanced capabilities:

10. **Rollback:**

Istio allows traffic policies to be quickly adjusted or rolled back, providing effective rollback options for failed updates.

11. **Scaling:**

Istio scales well with the application by efficiently distributing and dynamically adjusting network communication and management as needed.

12. **Blue/Green:**

Supports blue/green deployments to run versions concurrently and enable a seamless transition without downtime.

Strengths

1. **Extensive traffic control:**

Istio offers advanced traffic management capabilities that go well beyond simple routing. Administrators can define detailed route rules and traffic policies, such as A/B testing, canary releases, and time-delayed routing. These features enable fine-grained control of network traffic directly at the application level.

2. **Integrated telemetry and observability:**

Istio integrates seamlessly with a range of telemetry and observability tools such as Prometheus, Grafana, Jaeger and Kiali. These integrations provide deep insights into metrics, traces and logs, enabling detailed insights into network performance and microservices behavior.

3. **Advanced security features:**

In addition to mTLS for secure communication between services, Istio offers advanced security features such as end-user authentication via JWTs and fine-grained access controls. These mechanisms are valuable in security-critical enterprise environments.

4. **Policy and configuration management:**

Istio enables centralized management and updating of access and route policies through Custom Resource Definitions (CRDs) in Kubernetes. This facilitates governance and compliance in dynamic environments.

5. **Specialized ecosystem:**

- Istio has an ecosystem of specialized extensions and tools such as the Istio Operator, the Istio CNI Plugin and Citadel. These tools are specifically tailored to the requirements and architecture of Istio and provide optimized solutions for security, network management and service deployment.

6. Scalability and resilience:

Istio is specifically designed for use in large, distributed Kubernetes clusters. It supports enterprise-grade scalability and resiliency, providing mechanisms such as load balancing, circuit breaking, and automatic retries that help increase application availability and performance.

Weaknesses

- Complexity: Istio is known for its steep learning curve and complex configuration, which increases the barriers to entry.
- Resource consumption: Due to its extensive functionality, Istio can consume significant resources, which can lead to overloading in some environments.

Commercial Support

The following is an overview of various commercial support options for Istio as of Q2/2024:

No.	Provider	Istio Offering	City	Country	Homepage
1	Solo.io	Offers 24/7 support and SLAs for Istio, including patches and security updates. Cambridge	USA	Solo.io	
2	Altoros US	Custom support packages for installation and maintenance of Istio.	Sunnyvale	USA	Altoros US
3	Tetrade	Tetrade Istio Subscription with security audits and support for mission-critical environments.	San Francisco	USA	Tetrade
4	Altoros Europe	Localized support and compliance requirements for Istio in Europe.	Frankfurt am Main	Germany	Altoros Europe
5	InfraCloud Technologies	Implementation and maintenance of Istio with a focus on scalability and multi-cloud integration in Europe.	Frankfurt	Germany	InfraCloud

2. Linkerd

Linkerd is known for its easy installation and low resource consumption, which makes it particularly attractive for small to medium-sized Kubernetes clusters looking for a lightweight and fast service mesh.

Basic Features:

1. **Routing:** Linkerd provides simple and efficient request routing, supporting load balancing and dynamic routing for Canary releases.
2. **Security:** Linkerd provides automatic mTLS for all service-to-service communications, greatly enhancing security within the mesh without the need for complex configurations.
3. **Discovery:** As a service mesh, Linkerd automates service discovery across the Kubernetes cluster, making it easier to connect and manage services.
4. **Observability:** Linkerd collects and visualizes metrics such as latency, throughput, and error rates in an intuitive dashboard interface, without the need for additional instrumentation.

Interoperability:

5. Platforms:

Linkerd is primarily geared towards Kubernetes and makes optimal use of its orchestration and scaling capabilities.

6. **ECS support:**

Similar to Istio, Linkerd does not offer any specific integration options for Amazon's ECS.

7. **SMI compliance:**

Linkerd is not directly SMI-compliant because it uses its own set of APIs designed specifically for its architecture.

8. **Multi-mesh:**

Linkerd does not currently support a multi-mesh setup like Istio, but it focuses on simplicity and light-weighting within a single mesh.

9. **Protocols:**

- Supports HTTP, HTTP/2 and gRPC.
- Provides transparent proxy capabilities that do not require code change.

Advanced Capabilities:

10. **Rollback:**

Linkerd makes it possible to easily switch between different service versions through fast and precise traffic control mechanisms, providing effective rollback options during updates.

11. **Scaling:**

Linkerd is characterized by its low resource usage and high performance, making it suitable for even very large deployments.

12. **Blue/Green:**

Supports blue/green deployments through its advanced traffic management features that enable seamless transition and minimal disruptions.

Strengths

1. **Lightweight architecture:**

- Linkerd is known for its low resource utilization and high performance. It uses a minimalist architecture specifically designed to keep overhead as low as possible. This characteristic makes it ideal for small and medium-sized businesses or applications where every second of latency counts.

2. **Easy installation and configuration:**

- One of Linkerd's key features is its ease of use. It can be installed and configured in minutes, often with just a single command. This simplicity contrasts with many other service mesh solutions that require more complex setup.

3. **Automatic mTLS:**

While mTLS is supported by many service meshes, Linkerd stands out by automating this process. Linkerd enables mTLS by default and requires no additional configuration from users, greatly simplifying and improving the security of service communication.

4. **Transparent Proxy Implementation:**

– Linkerd uses a transparent proxy mechanism that requires no changes to application code. This means that applications integrated with a Linkerd service mesh can remain unchanged, making the introduction of a service mesh less disruptive.

5. **Built-in observability:**

– Linkerd offers comprehensive observability features right out of the box. It collects detailed metrics on latency, throughput, and error rates of all service interactions without requiring any additional configuration. This data is easily accessible via the Linkerd dashboard and provides valuable insights into the health of the system.

6. Community and foundation support:

- Linkerd is a Cloud Native Computing Foundation (CNCF) project, meaning it is backed by a broad and dedicated community. This ensures continuous development and support, as well as high stability and trustworthiness as an open-source project.

Weaknesses

- Limited protocol support: Linkerd focuses mainly on HTTP-based communication, which may limit its use in multi-protocol environments.
- Limited extensibility: It offers fewer extension possibilities compared to other service meshes such as Istio.

Commercial Support

Here is an overview of various commercial support options as of Q2/2024:

No.	Provider	Linkerd Offering	City	Country	Homepage
1	Buoyant	Offers direct commercial support, training, and architecture reviews. Enterprise version of Linkerd available. San Francisco	USA	Buoyant	
2	InfraCloud	Pune	India	InfraCloud	

3. Consul Connect

Consul Connect is a versatile solution that is particularly interesting for users who already use other parts of the Consul ecosystem or are looking for a solution that goes beyond simple container orchestration.

Basic features:

- 1. Routing:**
Enables simple routing and load balancing, supports intentions for communication control.
- 2. Security:**
Uses TLS for secure service communication, provides authentication and authorization.
- 3. Discovery:**
Integrated into the Consul ecosystem for comprehensive service discovery.
- 4. Observability:**
Provides metrics and logs for monitoring network performance.

Interoperability:

- 5. Platforms:**
Platform-independent, works with Kubernetes, VMs and bare metal.
- 6. ECS support:**
Can be used on Amazon ECS, requires manual configuration.
- 7. SMI compliance:**
Supports the SMI traffic access control specification, enables standardized service interactions while maintaining specific Consul functions.
- 8. Multi-mesh:**
Supports multi-data center deployments similar to a multi-mesh setup.
- 9. Protocols:**
 - Supports HTTP, TCP, and gRPC.
 - Can also apply fine-grained policies for specific protocols through its L7 routes.

Advanced capabilities:

- 10. Rollback:**
Consul enables efficient rollback through its version control capabilities and the ability to quickly review and reverse configuration changes. This is particularly useful in dynamic environments where rapid changes to service configuration are common. Consul's ability to store and revert states aids in the quick recovery of services after erroneous updates.
- 11. Scalability:**
Consul is particularly well known for its scalability, as it works efficiently in large networks with many nodes. It distributes network traffic and service discovery load across clusters, making it ideal for growing and changing environments. This is

supported by its distributed nature and the ability to connect multiple data centers, creating a robust and scalable infrastructure.

12. **Blue/Green:**

Consul Connect supports blue/green deployments through the use of service resolvers and service splitters, which enable fine-grained control of network traffic.

Strengths

1. **Seamless integration into the Consul ecosystem:**

– A key feature of Consul Connect is its integration into the broader Consul ecosystem, which provides service discovery, configuration management, and now network automation. This integration allows all aspects of service communication and management to be covered under a unified platform, reducing complexity and increasing consistency.

2. **Service mesh without third-party proxies:**

Consul Connect uses Envoy as its default proxy, but also offers the flexibility to function without any additional proxy software. This capability can reduce system complexity and improve performance, especially in environments where minimal latency and overhead are critical.

3. **“Intentions” for high security and control:**

Consul Connect uses “intentions” to govern access between services. Intentions are highly configurable, centrally managed rules that determine which services are allowed to communicate with each other. This model provides a strong layer of security because network traffic is controlled based on service identities, not just IP addresses.

4. **Ease of scalability and multi-platform support:**

Consul Connect is uniquely positioned to function in a variety of environments, including Kubernetes, Nomad, and even directly on virtual machines. This broad support enables organizations to leverage a unified service mesh across multiple platforms and technologies.

5. **Built-in certificate management:**

Consul Connect offers automated certificate management that strengthens security by automatically rotating and managing TLS certificates for service-to-service communication. This reduces the manual effort and complexity associated with certificate management.

6. **Best-in-class network performance:**

Consul Connect's direct integration with the operating system and use of kernel technologies enables it to deliver impressive network performance. This makes it ideal for performance-critical applications and large distributed systems.

Weaknesses

– **More limited community and resources:** Although well established, Consul may not have the same scale or developer community engagement as some other service mesh solutions, which can limit access to tutorials, best practices and third-party integrations.

Complexity of security policies: While the use of “intentions” for security control provides fine-grained access control, it can be complex to set up and manage in large or dynamic environments.

Commercial Support

Commercial offerings are available almost exclusively from Hashicorp directly. Currently, 4/24, there is a rumor that IBM is taking over the company.

Here are the various offers:

- Technical support: Help with installation, configuration and operation of Consul Connect, including troubleshooting and performance optimization.
 - Training and Certification: Offers training to effectively use Consul Connect and certification programs that validate expertise in the application.
- Architecture consulting: Expert advice on how to best implement Consul Connect in specific enterprise environments, customized to individual requirements and business objectives.
- Support levels bronze to silver define corresponding SLAs.

Subsidiaries:

No.	Corp	City	Country	Homepage
1	HashiCorp US	San Francisco	USA	HashiCorp
2	HashiCorp Europe	London	United Kingdom	HashiCorp UK
3	HashiCorp Europe	Berlin	Germany	HashiCorp DE
4	HashiCorp Europe	Amsterdam	Netherlands	HashiCorp NL
5	HashiCorp Europe	Dublin	Ireland	HashiCorp IE

4. AWS App Mesh

AWS App Mesh

AWS App Mesh offers deep integration into the AWS ecosystem, making it an attractive choice for AWS users looking for a native service mesh solution.

Basic Features:

1. **Routing:**

AWS App Mesh offers detailed routing and supports canary deployments for incremental traffic management.

2. **Security:**

Supports mTLS for secure communication between services and offers comprehensive authentication and authorization options.

3. **Discovery:**

Integrated with AWS Cloud Map for service discovery, allows dynamic registration and discovery of services.

4. **Observability:**

Provides integrated monitoring with detailed metrics, logs, and tracing for performance monitoring.

Interoperability:

5. **Platforms:**

Deeply integrated into the AWS ecosystem, optimized for use with ECS, EKS, Fargate, and EC2.

6. **ECS support:**

Fully supported and optimized for use with Amazon ECS.

7. **SMI compliance:**

App Mesh does not follow the SMI specification but uses AWS-specific standards.

8. **Multi-Mesh:**

Does not explicitly support multi-mesh configurations.

9. **Protocols**

- Supports HTTP, HTTP/2, gRPC, and TCP protocols.
- Provides specific routing rules for the supported protocols.

Advanced Capabilities:

10. **Rollback:**

Does not provide direct rollback mechanisms, but enables effective management of service versions and rapid response to problems through advanced traffic control and canary deployments.

11. **Scaling:**

Scales seamlessly with AWS infrastructure and supports dynamic adjustments to resource requirements.

12. **Blue/Green:**

AWS App Mesh supports blue/green deployments through traffic-shifting capabilities that can be used to gradually redirect traffic between different versions of the application.

Strengths

1. Performance and resource consumption:

AWS App Mesh is specifically designed to optimize and function in the AWS cloud environment. It uses AWS-specific optimizations to minimize latency and efficiently manage resource consumption. As a cloud-native solution, it is tightly integrated with AWS services such as ECS, EKS, and EC2, which optimizes performance in AWS infrastructures.

2. AWS integration:

- Integration with the AWS ecosystem offers a significant advantage in terms of usability. **AWS App Mesh** is seamlessly integrated into the AWS Management Console, making it easier to set up and manage the service mesh. AWS customers can use their existing AWS skills and tools to effectively manage the mesh without having to learn new systems.

3. Extensibility:

While **AWS App Mesh** is designed primarily for use within the AWS ecosystem, it provides extensibility through APIs and integration with AWS Lambda. This allows users to implement custom control and management logic to customize the mesh for specific requirements.

4. Support and documentation:

As an AWS service, **AWS App Mesh** benefits from the extensive documentation, professional support options, and resources that AWS provides. Users have access to a wide range of guides, tutorials, and community forums supported by AWS, as well as the option of receiving direct support from AWS.

5. Security features:

AWS App Mesh provides strong security features that are tightly integrated with other AWS security services. These include automatic encryption of traffic using mTLS, integration with AWS IAM for access management, and the ability to manage security policies centrally through the AWS Management Console. This integration ensures that security practices are consistent with AWS best practices and facilitates security management at scale.

Weaknesses

AWS-centricity: App Mesh is deeply integrated into the AWS ecosystem, which may be less appealing to users outside of AWS.

Functionality limitations: May be limited in terms of multicluster and multi-cloud capabilities.

- UX experience:** Many scattered configurations that are not always easy to find make familiarization with the product extremely difficult and increase the potential for errors.

Commercial support

AWS also offers comprehensive support for App Mesh through the AWS Partner Network, which includes a wide range of providers that offer specialized services and support for AWS App Mesh and other AWS services. These partners help organizations implement and optimize App Mesh through consulting, integration, and managed services. They also help apply security and efficiency best practices across multiple AWS environments, see: [AWS Partner Site](#)

5. Service Fabric Mesh

Azure Service Fabric Mesh, or Azure SFM for short, is particularly suitable for developers looking for solutions that are deeply integrated into the Azure ecosystem.

Basic features:

1. Routing:

Azure Service Fabric Mesh provides intelligent traffic routing and support for both stateless and stateful microservices to enable efficient container orchestration.

2. Security:

It integrates with Azure Active Directory and supports secret management via Azure Key Vault, enabling secure identity management and access control.

3. Discovery:

Service Fabric Mesh facilitates service discovery within the mesh.

4. Observability:

It supports monitoring and management throughout the entire application lifecycle and is integrated into CI/CD tools such as Azure Pipelines and Jenkins.

Interoperability:

5. Platforms:

Service Fabric Mesh supports both Windows and Linux containers and enables development in any programming language and framework.

6. ECS support:

Not available as a pure Azure solution.

7. SMI compliance:

No information available.

8. Multi-mesh:

Not documented.

9. Protocols:

- Focuses primarily on HTTP and TCP.
- Does not offer any specific mention of gRPC.

Advanced capabilities:

10. Rollback

Not documented.

11. Scaling:

Automatic scaling based on CPU or memory usage is available, which makes it easier to adjust resources according to the load.

12. Blue/Green:

No direct support.

Strengths

1. Performance and resource consumption:

Azure Service Fabric Mesh is optimally integrated into the Azure cloud environment, enabling it to efficiently manage performance and resource consumption. It benefits from tight coupling with Azure resources, enabling automatic scaling and resource optimization as needed.

2. Ease of use:

As a fully managed service, **Azure Service Fabric Mesh** provides a particularly user-friendly experience by reducing the complexity of cluster management and orchestration. Users can focus on developing their microservices without having to worry about the infrastructure. Integration with Azure DevOps for CI/CD workflows also promotes efficient development practices.

3. Extensibility:

Azure Service Fabric Mesh offers a flexible and extensible architecture that allows developers to work in any programming language and framework. Although built specifically for Azure, it supports both Windows and Linux containers, improving interoperability within the Azure platform.

4. Support and documentation:

As part of the Azure ecosystem, **Azure Service Fabric Mesh** benefits from Microsoft's extensive support and network of resources. Documentation is comprehensive and constantly updated to help developers implement and use Service Mesh. Microsoft also offers various support plans, ranging from basic support to personalized support for large enterprises.

5. Security features:

Azure Service Fabric Mesh integrates seamlessly with Azure Security Center, enabling end-to-end security from infrastructure to application code. Using Azure Active Directory for authentication and Azure Key Vault for managing secrets provides a robust security foundation that is specifically tailored to the needs of Azure users.

Weaknesses

- **Proprietary technology:** As part of the Azure platform, it is mainly restricted to Azure users and offers less flexibility for multi-cloud or on-premises scenarios.
- **Limited community:** It has a smaller developer community compared to open-source solutions.

Commercial support

offers commercial support for Azure Service Fabric Mesh in various levels of support plans, including:

Developer: ideal for test and development environments. Provides unlimited 24/7 access to technical support engineers via email.

Standard: Provides faster access to support engineers and implementation assistance, ideal for production environments in small and medium-sized businesses.

Professional Direct: Offers fast response times and proactive support from an assigned account manager, suitable for critical dependencies in large organizations.

Premier: Offers the most extensive support experience, including all Professional Direct benefits, as well as proactive support, advice, and operational assistance tailored to the organization's unique needs.

6. Traefik Mesh

Traefik Mesh is characterized by easy installation and a non-invasive architecture, as it does not require a sidecar container, making it a lightweight and low-maintenance option for Kubernetes environments.

Basic features:

1. Routing:

Traefik Mesh supports complex routing mechanisms such as load balancing, retries, failovers, circuit breakers and rate limits, enabling fine-grained traffic control.

2. Security:

Traefik Mesh meets the SMI specifications and offers features such as mTLS for secure communication between services and access controls via access control lists.

3. Discovery:

As a Kubernetes-native solution, Traefik Mesh integrates seamlessly into the existing Kubernetes infrastructure and supports efficient service discovery.

4. Observability:

Offers comprehensive observability features, including support for OpenTracing, which enables integration with common tracing systems. Metrics are directly available through the pre-installed Prometheus and Grafana setups.

Interoperability:

5. Platforms:

Traefik Mesh is designed and optimized for Kubernetes, so it can be used with any Kubernetes installation.

6. ECS support:

There is no support for ECS.

7. SMI compliance:

Traefik Mesh supports the Service Mesh Interface (SMI) specification.

8. Multi-Mesh:

No information is provided on multi-mesh support.

9. Protocols:

- Mainly supports HTTP and HTTP/2.
- No explicit mention of gRPC.

Advanced features:

10. Rollback:

While specific rollback features are not highlighted, Traefik Mesh's ease of configuration and rapid deployment capability allows for quick customization and correction of network configurations.

11. Scaling:

Leverages Kubernetes autoscaling.

12. **Blue/Green:**

Can support complex deployment strategies such as Blue/Green or Canary through its advanced traffic shift.

Strengths

1. Sidecar-free architecture:

- A key unique selling point of **Traefik Mesh** is its architectural decision to avoid sidecar proxies. This decision reduces resource consumption and complexity in the network by centrally managing network traffic without the need for additional proxies for each service.

2. Easy integration with Traefik Ingress:

For users already using Traefik as an Ingress controller, **Traefik Mesh** offers a particularly smooth integration. This seamless connection between Ingress and the service mesh is particularly advantageous for managing end-to-end HTTP/HTTPS requests within a Kubernetes cluster.

3. Plug-and-play middleware:

- **Traefik Mesh** enables the easy integration of middleware components developed as part of the Traefik ecosystem. This allows users to add specific features such as header manipulation, rate limiting or advanced circuit breakers with little configuration effort.

4. Centralized management dashboard:

Another unique selling point is the central dashboard that Traefik offers for its products. This dashboard simplifies the monitoring and management of network traffic and configurations via a user-friendly interface that provides real-time updates.

Weaknesses

- **Young technology:** As a relatively new product on the market, Traefik Mesh may be less mature and offer fewer features than more established solutions.
- **Community size:** Support and resources may be limited compared to other larger projects.

Commercial Support

Traefik offers commercial support directly through Traefik Labs. This support is specifically designed for customers who have critical deployment environments and includes:

Mission Critical Support: Here, there are different response times based on the severity of the problem. For critical issues (severity 1-2), Traefik Labs guarantees a response time within 2 hours, available 24/7/365. For less critical issues (severity 3-4), Traefik offers a response time within 8 hours during normal business hours.

~~7. NGINX Service Mesh~~

No longer developed since Q1/24!

8. Rancher

Rancher itself is not a service mesh at its core, but it integrates Istio and Kiali together, thus offering something like its own “Istio distribution”. It places a particular focus on user-friendliness and advanced network functions.

Basic features:

1. Routing:

Rancher supports advanced routing capabilities by integrating Istio, including traffic control for blue/green and canary deployments.

2. Security:

Rancher provides robust security features by integrating Istio, including mTLS to encrypt internal service traffic.

3. Discovery:

Rancher itself does not provide any special service discovery component. Instead, it uses Kubernetes' native service discovery capabilities. Kubernetes has a built-in service discovery mechanism that allows containers to find each other via DNS name and communicate.

4. Observability:

Rancher offers comprehensive monitoring and tracing capabilities through integration with tools such as Prometheus and Grafana.

Interoperability:

5. Platforms:

Rancher is platform-independent and supports various Kubernetes environments such as EKS, AKS, GKE and standalone Kubernetes installations.

6. ECS support:

Not available.

7. SMI compliance:

Rancher integrates Istio, which partially supports the SMI specifications and thus offers standardized service mesh functions.

8. Multi-mesh:

Rancher enables the management of Istio across multiple clusters, which supports a multi-mesh setup.

9. Protocols

- Inherits protocol support from Istio, i.e. HTTP, HTTP/2, gRPC, TCP, etc.
- Uses Istio's protocol detection and control capabilities.

Advanced features:

10. Rollback:

Not directly. Through the traffic steering capabilities in Istio, Rancher can redirect traffic to earlier versions of services, which is similar to a rollback.

11. Scaling:

Rancher offers extensive scaling capabilities for managing large and complex Kubernetes clusters.

12. **Blue/Green:**

powered by Istio, Rancher enables Blue/Green deployments facilitated by advanced traffic control.

Strengths

1. Istio and Kiali integration:

- Rancher stands out by seamlessly integrating Istio, one of the leading service mesh implementations. This integration not only provides Istio's core features, but also the advanced visualization and management capabilities of Kiali, a tool for visualizing and managing Istio service meshes.

2. Ease of use in managing clusters:

– A key differentiator of Rancher is its comprehensive user interface that simplifies the management of Kubernetes clusters and Istio service meshes. Rancher allows administrators to configure and manage Istio functions through a graphical interface, reducing complexity and increasing accessibility.

3. Multi-cluster management:

– Rancher offers outstanding capabilities for managing multi-cluster environments. It enables centralized management and monitoring of multiple Kubernetes clusters from a single console. This is particularly valuable for organizations operating large, distributed environments that require consistent policy application and service mesh configuration across multiple clusters.

4. Platform independence:

Rancher supports a wide range of Kubernetes environments, including popular cloud services such as AWS EKS, Azure AKS, and Google GKE, as well as on-premises installations. This flexibility makes Rancher an attractive option for organizations that operate a heterogeneous infrastructure but still want a unified management solution.

5. Extensibility through apps and catalogs:

Rancher makes it easy to add and manage applications through its integrated app catalog, which includes a wide range of pre-packaged apps and tools. This enables users to quickly add new features and services to their cluster, including additional service mesh capabilities and security tools.

Weaknesses

- **Specific integrations:** The heavy reliance on Istio could be limiting for users looking for a more flexible or independent solution.
- **Complexity:** Managing multi-cluster can be complex and requires a good understanding of the underlying technologies.

Commercial Support

Rancher, now part of SUSE, offers commercial support directly through SUSE Rancher. Here are the details of their commercial support offerings:

Rancher Prime: Provides SLA-backed enterprise support for Rancher that offers access to proven delivery mechanisms to manage and operate Kubernetes deployments with a high level of confidence. Rancher Prime is designed to meet the needs of organizations that require a highly reliable and secure container management solution.

- <https://rancher.com/>

9. Kuma

Kuma is a versatile service mesh built on Envoy that can be used effectively in both Kubernetes and VM environments.

Ideal for organizations seeking a flexible and extensible architecture and looking to deploy a unified service mesh solution across different cloud platforms and technologies.

Basic Features:

1. Routing:

Kuma supports complex routing strategies including load balancing and can direct traffic based on various parameters.

2. Security:

Kuma offers comprehensive security features, including Mutual TLS (mTLS) for all traffic layers, ensuring secure communication within the mesh.

3. Discovery:

Kuma enables efficient service discovery in distributed environments, facilitating microservices management.

4. Observability:

Integrated with tools such as Prometheus and Grafana for monitoring and visualizing metrics and logs, it also supports tracing for detailed tracking of service interactions.

Interoperability:

5. Platforms:

Supports a wide range of environments, including Kubernetes, VMs and bare metal.

6. ECS support:

Kuma also supports AWS ECS. This is made possible by Kuma's ability to work efficiently not only in Kubernetes and VM-based environments, but also in containerized environments such as ECS. This makes Kuma a versatile solution for various platforms and technologies. Kuma offers native support for AWS ECS, making it easy to integrate ECS workloads within one or more service meshes.

7. SMI compliance:

No information available.

8. Multi-mesh:

Kuma supports native multi-mesh configurations that allow the simultaneous management of multiple isolated service meshes.

9. Protocols

- Supports HTTP, HTTP/2, TCP, gRPC, and more by using Envoy as the data plane*.

Advanced Capabilities:

10. Rollback:

Enables management of traffic policies that can facilitate rolling back changes, supported by its routing capabilities.

11. **Scaling:**

Designed to efficiently scale in large and complex environments, providing support for multi-zone and multi-cluster deployments.

12. **Blue/Green:**

Supports advanced deployment strategies such as Blue/Green and Canary, enabled by its comprehensive traffic control mechanisms.

Strengths

1. **Multi-mesh support:**

Kuma stands out with its native support for multi-mesh configurations, which allows administrators to manage multiple isolated service meshes within the same administrative domain. This is particularly useful for organizations that need to apply different security and routing policies in different parts of their infrastructure.

2. **Broad platform and environment support:**

Kuma is one of the few service mesh solutions that works seamlessly across a wide range of environments, including Kubernetes, VMs, and bare metal. This capability makes Kuma particularly attractive for organizations that have a mixed infrastructure or that are migrating incrementally from VMs to containers.

3. **Automatic sidecar injection:**

Kuma offers automatic sidecar injection for Kubernetes, which simplifies the deployment and management of the service mesh. This automation helps to reduce human error and speeds up the process of service mesh integration.

4. **Global and remote control plane architecture:**

Another unique feature of Kuma is its architecture, which supports a global control plane that can manage multiple remote control planes in different clusters or regions. This architecture is ideal for organizations with geographically distributed infrastructures and supports high availability and fault tolerance.

5. **Advanced security and traffic control features:**

Kuma offers advanced security features that go beyond standard mTLS. This includes support for traffic permissions, traffic routing, traffic tracing, circuit breakers, fault injection, and more. These comprehensive features enable administrators to implement very specific security and traffic management policies.

6. **Native support for AWS ECS:**

Kuma is one of the few service meshes to offer native support for AWS ECS. This allows ECS workloads to be seamlessly integrated into a Kuma service mesh, which is a unique option for AWS users.

Weaknesses

Younger product: As a newer product on the market, Kuma may not yet have the same maturity and stability as its competitors.

- **Limited adoption:** The lesser awareness and usage compared to Istio or Linkerd might pose a challenge for some organizations.

Commercial support:

Kuma is developed and supported by Kong Inc., so commercial support is provided directly by Kong. Kong provides a wide range of services and support for Kuma, including:

Enterprise Support: Kong offers dedicated enterprise support for Kuma that includes priority access to technical support teams, 24/7 emergency support, and access to maintenance

updates and patches.

Consulting and Integration: Kong also offers professional services including consulting on implementing and optimizing Kuma in enterprise environments, as well as integration with other systems and technologies.

- <https://konghq.com/>

10. Cilium

Cilium is distinguished by its innovative use of eBPF* that sets it apart from other service mesh solutions. This technology allows Cilium to overcome many of the performance and complexity issues associated with more traditional, proxy-based service meshes

Basic Features:

1. Routing:

Cilium enables complex routing mechanisms, including load balancing and resource-efficient traffic control through direct integration into the Linux kernel using eBPF.

2. Security:

Provides advanced security features, including mTLS and identity-based security mechanisms that ensure secure communication between services.

3. Discovery:

Cilium supports efficient service discovery that is integrated into its core functions and enables high performance even in complex network topologies.

4. Observability:

Supports extensive observation functions, which are enhanced by eBPF to provide a detailed view of network communication.

Interoperability:

5. Platforms:

Cilium runs natively on Kubernetes and can be deployed in any cloud environment or on its own servers.

6. ECS support:

No

7. SMI compliance:

No specific information available.

8. Multi-mesh:

Supports complex scenarios with multiple service meshes and multi-cluster configurations through its advanced networking capabilities.

9. Protocols

- Supports a wide range of protocols, including HTTP, TCP, gRPC, Kafka, and DNS, thanks to eBPF*.
- Provides advanced security and performance features that work directly at the kernel level to maximize efficiency.

Advanced capabilities:

10. Rollback:

While Cilium does not explicitly document specific rollback capabilities, its comprehensive network policies and dynamic configuration management allow settings to be quickly reset.

11. Scalability:

Cilium is highly scalable, supported by the efficiency of eBPF, which makes it possible to scale network performance and security without significant overheads.

12. Blue/Green:

Supports advanced deployment strategies through its traffic control and security features.

Strengths

1. Leveraging eBPF technology:

- One of the most outstanding features of Cilium is the use of the extended Berkeley Packet Filter (eBPF) technology. eBPF allows Cilium to operate directly in the Linux

kernel, enabling significantly improved network performance and security. This approach offers considerable advantages in terms of efficiency and speed, by enforcing network and security policies at a very low system level.

2. Transparent security policies:

- Cilium enables the enforcement of security policies at the application level by identifying and controlling individual functions within an application without requiring code changes. This ability to transparently enforce security measures supports finer control and better adaptability to dynamic threats.

3. Advanced network and service mesh functions:

In addition to traditional service mesh functions, Cilium supports network functions that go beyond the usual service mesh capabilities. These include native support for multi-cluster networks, L4 and L7 level load balancing, and direct API call visibility, enabling deeper network inspection and management.

4. High scalability and multitenancy:

Cilium is particularly suitable for large, distributed, and multi-tenant environments. Scalability is achieved by efficiently processing network policies in the kernel, ensuring consistent performance even in very large clusters.

5. Support for a wide range of protocols:

By leveraging eBPF, Cilium can support a wide range of network protocols, including TCP, UDP, HTTP/2, and gRPC. This capability allows Cilium to function effectively in various application architectures and communication patterns.

6. Seamless integration into existing environments:

Cilium can be easily integrated into existing Kubernetes installations and other orchestration platforms, without the need for extensive changes to existing applications or infrastructure.

Weaknesses

- Specific requirements: The use of eBPF can add complexity for some users and requires specific technical know-how.
- Kernel dependencies: Since eBPF operates at the kernel level, Cilium may depend on specific kernel versions. Cilium therefore cannot easily work on serverless container infrastructures, such as Fargate.

Commercial Support

Isovalent offers "Isovalent Cilium Enterprise", an extended version of Cilium that is specifically designed for enterprise environments and offers additional security and performance features in addition to the core offering.

Enhanced security: Hardened versions of Cilium that include regular security updates and patches.

Professional support: 24/7 access to Cilium experts to provide support and guidance on implementing and operating Cilium.

Performance monitoring and optimization: Tools and advice on how to optimize network performance and efficiency.

Isovalent is aimed at large companies and organizations that require a robust and scalable network solution, and offers customized solutions tailored to the specific requirements and compliance requirements of its customers.

<https://isovalent.com/>

Properties in detail

1. Basic properties:

1. Routing:

This includes the service mesh's ability to route traffic between services, including advanced routing rules, traffic splitting, and traffic shifting.

2. Security:

This is about the mesh's security features such as mTLS encryption, authentication, and access controls to ensure secure communication between services.

3. Discovery:

This feature enables automatic service discovery and a service registry to dynamically discover and configure services.

4. Observability:

This is the mesh's ability to monitor and analyze service performance and health, including monitoring and tracing for troubleshooting and analysis.

2. Interoperability

5. Platforms:

Support for various platforms such as Kubernetes, ECS, Nomad, VMs or bare metal infrastructures.

6. ECS support:

This is specifically about support for and integration with AWS Elastic Container Service (ECS) for managing container workloads.

7. SMI compliance:

This refers to the conformance of the service mesh with the Service Mesh Interface (SMI), a standard for unifying service mesh capabilities.

8. **Multi-mesh capability:**

This enables the management and integration of multiple service mesh instances in an environment.

9. **Protocols:**

- **HTTP/HTTP2:** Support for web protocols, essential for modern web applications.
- **gRPC:** Important for microservices architectures that require efficient, cross-platform communication.
- **TCP:** Basic support for lower network layers.
- **WebSockets:** Supports real-time communication applications.
- **Others** (e.g. MQTT, AMQP, Kafka): Specific support for messaging protocols used in IoT and other event-driven architectures.

3. **Advanced capabilities**

10. **Rollback:**

This is the ability to reverse changes to configuration or traffic to return to a previous stable version.

11. **Scaling:**

This feature describes the ability of the service mesh to handle an increasing number of services and traffic while maintaining high performance and availability.

12. **Blue/Green Deployment:**

This is a deployment method that involves operating two separate environments simultaneously to seamlessly implement updates or changes and minimize downtime.

4. **Strengths and weaknesses**

The strengths include unique selling points and, in "SWOT style", some weaknesses are also mentioned.

5. **Commercial offers**

Whether SaaS, training, real-time support or certification offers. Not always can or should you want to do everything yourself. Even if most products are available with their repos as FOSS, this does not mean that they are easy to use. Therefore, possible offers, mostly commercial, are mentioned here for the products.

Glossary

SOA:

Service Oriented Architecture

SideCar Proxy:

In container orchestration systems such as AWS ECS (Elastic Container Service) and AWS EKS (Elastic Kubernetes Service), sidecar proxies can be implemented with each container instance as additional containers within the same task (in ECS) or pod (in EKS) to control network traffic, security policies, and monitoring functions at a more granular level, without disrupting the main applications.

The **data plane**

(data flow level) in a network is responsible for the transmission of user data and performs operations such as routing, load balancing, and packet filtering based on the policies dictated by the control plane.

The **control plane**

(control plane) is responsible for managing and configuring the network by deciding how data should flow through the network and implements appropriate policies and rules for the data plane.

eBPF:

eBPF stands for “extended Berkeley Packet Filter” and is a highly flexible and powerful technology in the Linux kernel that allows code to be executed securely and efficiently directly in the kernel. Originally developed for network filtering, eBPF has become a general runtime environment that supports many different functions.

Ingress controller

An Ingress Controller is a critical component of a Kubernetes network that manages the rules for routing external HTTP and HTTPS traffic (i.e., requests from the Internet) to the internal services within a Kubernetes cluster. Ingress Controllers are specifically designed to control access to services at a higher level than the simple IP-based routing rules of the Kubernetes service.